

Improvement in the Adhesive Property of Chemically Stable Polymeric Materials and FRP

H. Kanazawa* and A. Inada

Department of Industrial Systems, Faculty of Symbiotic Systems Science,
Fukushima University, 1 Kanayagawa, Fukushima 960-1296, Japan

* Corresponding author (kana@sss.fukushima-u.ac.jp)

Keywords: *polyolefins, silicone resin, fluorine resin, adhesive property, water-based paint, engineering plastics, FRP*

1 Introduction

Polyolefins such as polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE) or ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMPE) and poly(methyl pentene) (PMP), etc. have both high tensile strength and resistance to chemical reagents.

However, these materials have no hydrophilic property and no adhesive property because of the hydro carbon molecular structure. Many techniques were carried out to modify the surface property of polyolefins[1,2]. Durable improvements for polyolefin materials were not obtained. For instance, corona or plasma treatment is generally used to improve the adhesive property. PE or PP materials are treated by the corona discharge treatment, the subsequent process using adhesives have to be rapidly carried out. In addition, the corona discharge treatment is not effective for some polymeric materials. When many numbers of large polymeric materials are bonded to each other or other materials, it is desirable to carry out the adhesive process quickly after the discharge treatment. Cyanoacrylate adhesives with primers are sometimes useful for the adhesion of polyolefin materials. But, they do not give high adhesive force, and they are too expensive to apply for large materials.

We studied the modification of polyolefins and other chemically stable polymeric materials such as polyethylene (PE), ultrahigh molecular weight PE (UHMWPE), polycarbonate (PC), polyester, silicone and fluorocarbon resins, etc. and found that the combination of several conventional methods was effective for the improvement in the adhesive property.[3,4] In addition, the modification of engineering plastics such as polyoxymethylene

(POM, polyacetal), polybutyleneterephthalate (PBT), polyamides, polysulfone (PS), polyimide (PI), polyether ether ketone (PEEK), and fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) was carried out. We aimed at the durable adhesion improvement of the chemically stable polymeric materials using general kinds of adhesives.

2 Experimental

2.1 Polymeric materials Fibers, films, sheets, boards, rods and tubes of polymeric materials were provided by companies or commercial products were obtained. They were washed with methanol before use. Typical standards; PP non-woven fabrics (unit weight 50g/m²), PP film and plates (thickness 100μm–2.00mm), UHMWPE (average molecular weight 5,000,000-8,000,000) plates (unit weight 467g /m²) and films (thickness 60, 100μm, weight 30, 83 g /m²), PET films (weight 72g /m²), PC plates (thickness 100μm–1.00mm), silicone resins and fluorine resins, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), ethylenetetrafluoroethylene copolymer (PETFE) etc.) (thickness 100μm–1.50mm) were used. Boards of POM, polybutyleneterephthalate (PBT), polyamides, PS, PI, polyether ether ketone (PEEK), and carbonfiber FRP (CFRP) of PEEK were provided by the Tohoku-Konan Co. Ltd., Japan.

2.2 Adhesives Commercial polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) glue, wood bond (aqueous polyvinylacetate 41 wt% solution), cyanoacrylate (CA) with or without primers, the Quick five (Konishi Com. Ltd., Japan); epoxy resin bond (two liquid mixed type) were used.

2.3 Paint Commercial water-based paint (Asahipen, Co. Ltd., Japan) which contains synthetic resins (acrylic, silicone and fluorocarbon resins), pigments and organic solvents and water-based urethane car-use paint was used. The peeling test of the coated paint was carried out by the cross-cut test, JIS K5400.

2.4 Treatment

Polymeric materials were activated by chemical oxidation, or energy irradiations such as UV, plasma, and high-voltage electric discharge treatment. Activated polymeric materials were subsequently treated with solutions of polymers, monomers or other chemical reagents in the presence of catalysts or initiators. Some catalysts or initiators were added in the mixture.

Polymeric materials were taken out of the reaction mixture and washed with solvents or detergent solutions.

2.5 Measurements

The tensile shear strength, 180° or T-peel tests were carried out to observe the adhesive strength of untreated or modified materials bonded with adhesives by a tensile tester, Shimadzu AGS-H5KN. IR spectra of polymeric materials were observed by a Shimadzu IRPrestige-21 equipped with a Smiths DuraSampl IR II (ATR accessory).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Activation process and reaction mechanism

In the activation process, polymeric materials are oxidized. The oxidation extent was observed by FTIR. IR spectra of untreated PP and treated PP oxidized in the activation process were obtained by the ATR method. The treated polymeric materials gave an adsorption peak based on carbonyl groups around 1710 cm⁻¹. The plot of the area ratio at a peak at around 1710 cm⁻¹ against treatment time gave a straight line. It was important to carry out the activation process only slightly on the material surface in order to avoid the degradation. Activated polymeric materials were subsequently reacted with polymer or other chemical reagents to modify the material surface. It is not necessary to carry out the reaction process rapidly after the activation process.

Even when the activated materials were laid some weeks, the subsequent treatment was attained well. The reaction mechanism was speculated, considering the references. [5-8] The mechanism is given in Scheme 1. Polymeric materials are oxidized in the activation process and hydroperoxyl groups are formed. As the groups are not stable, some of them are considered to be changed to the other functional groups. These groups are considered to react with chemical reagents (RX).

Scheme 1 Mechanism

3.2 Improvement in the adhesive property of polymeric materials

The adhesive property of polymeric materials was improved well by the present method. Modified PP boards could be bonded to other materials with usual adhesives, and the material failure was observed in the tensile strength test of bonded materials. Figure 1 gives the specimen of PP board used in the tensile shear strength test.

Fig.1 Tensile shear strength test of PP board bonded to aluminum board; right, PP and left, aluminum board.

The adhesive strength of pressure sensitive adhesive double-coated tapes was also improved by the present technique. Figure 2 gives a modified PP-made towel hunger bonded strongly to a metal wall, using a double-coated tape. The peeling strength was increased to over 3 kgf from 300 gf.

Fig.2 Modified PP-made towel hunger bonded to a metal wall with double-coated

Though usual silicone rubber materials give water-repellency and no adhesive property, the modified silicone polymer materials got wet in water and could be bonded to wood boards using a commercial wood glue (PVA and polyvinylacetate). Figure 3 shows the specimen of silicone resin sheets bonded to wooden boards with a wood glue and used in the adhesive strength test. Untreated silicone rubber sheet bonded to wooden board gave an interfacial failure, but

modified one gave a material failure in the shear strength test.

The modified silicone resin sheet was bonded to aluminum board with wood glue and epoxy resin adhesive (Quick 5). The values in the shear strength test were given in Table 1.

Fig.3 Silicone resin sheets bonded to wooden boards with a wood glue and used in the tensile strength test; right, silicone and left, wooden boards.

Table 1 Shear strength test of silicone resin

Adherend	Wood		Aluminum	
	Untreated	Modified	Untreated	Modified
Used adhesive	Wood glue		Epoxy resin (two components)	
Shear strength (MPa)	0.05	0.11	0.05	0.14
Failure style	Si-resin failure	Interfacial failure	Si-resin failure	Interfacial failure

Modified PC boards were bonded to paper with starch or PVA glues (Figure 4).

Fig.4 T-peel test of PC plates bonded to paper; untreated PC (left) and treated PC (right)

Modified PEEK boards were bonded to each other with an urethane adhesive and the adhesive shear strength test was carried out; a material failure of PEEK boards was occurred at 6.30MPa as given in Figure 5, while the untreated ones gave an interfacial failure at 1.17MPa. The adhesiveness of PEEK was improved well.

Fig.5 Modified PEEK boards used in the adhesive shear strength test

The adhesiveness of fluorocarbon resins, PTFE, PETFE, PFA and PVDF materials was improved well by the present process. The modified materials were adhered to aluminum boards using Quick 5 (adhesive containing epoxy resin and polythiol) and other adhesives and the cohesive failure was observed in the peel test. Figure 6 gives modified PTFE boards bonded to rubber sheet and aluminum board with a polycyanoacrylate adhesive, and a paper with wood glue.

Fig.6 Modified PTFE board bonded to to black rubber (upper), paper and aluminum (lower).

3.3 FRP modification

The adhesiveness of carbon fiber FRP (CFRP) boards was improved well by the present modification. Especially, the modified materials gave the adhesive strength several years after the modification. FRP boards made of carbon fiber-PEEK or carbon-fiber-epoxy resin were modified and the adhesiveness with various adhesives was improved.

It is noteworthy that when modified PP fibers were used in the epoxy resin, the PP fibers were not run away from the resin in the shear strength test (Figure 7, right), though untreated PP fibers were simply run out. The PP-FRP was not separated after the yield point in the tensile strength test, though glass-fiber FRP and CFRP were broken to two pieces.

Fig.7 FRP specimens after the three-point bending test; untreated PP (left), and modified PP (right)

3.4 Comparison with corona-discharge treatment

Corona discharge treatment was widely applied to improve the adhesiveness of polyolefin and other materials. In general, this treatment and subsequent coating process are successively carried out in the production plant. When corona discharged PP materials were laid for several days, its adhesive property was extremely decreased.

3.5 Solvent bonding

Modified polybutadine, PP, silicone rubber tubes were connected to each other by solvent bonding (without any adhesives). Figure 8 gives silicone rubber tube bonded to a PP tube (T-tube) with usual organic solvent. This technique is applicable for the medical devices.

Fig.8 Silicone rubber tubes connected to a PP T-tube by solvent bonding

3.6 Water-based paint coating

Modified PE, UHMWPE, PP, PC, PET, silicone and fluorocarbon resins, etc. were coated well with water-based paints. Figure 9 gives the result of the cross-cut test for PP plate coated with water-based acrylic paint. The upper specimen gives a PP plate treated incompletely and the lower one modified well. The upper PP gave 0/100 but the lower PP gave a full-mark, 100/100 in the cross-cut test.

The cross-cut test of water-based paint coated UHMWPE boards is given in Figure 10; the upper specimens are untreated ones; the left, before the test and the right, after the test. The under specimens are modified ones; the left, before the test and the right, after the test. The modified UHMWPE board gave a full-mark, 100/100.

Fig.9 Modified and coated PP boards used in the cross-cut test; upper : incompletely and lower : completely modified ones.

Fig.10 Water-based paint coated UHMWPE boards; upper two: untreated ones, lower two: modified ones. Each right one gave the specimens examined by the cross-cut test.

Usually, PTFE materials are modified under strict chemical conditions. On the other hand, the present process gives modified PTFE ones under a calm conditions. A PTFE sheet was modified and coated with water-based paint. Figure 11 gives the untreated and modified PTFE sheets.

Fig.11 Water-based paint coated PTFE sheets; upper: untreated one, lower: modified ones.

3.7 Comparison of corona-discharge treatment and the present process in the coating of silicone resin sheets

Silicone rubber sheets were modified by usual corona discharge treatment and the present technique. Figure 12 gives the results; all silicone rubber sheets were coated with a water-based paint (Water Super Coat of Asahi-pen Co. Ltd.). Although the corona-discharged silicone rubber sheet could be coated with the paint immediately after the treatment, it could not be coated 5 hours after the treatment. On the other hand, the silicone rubber treated by our method gave good coating property even 120 days after the treatment. As a fact, the modified and coated materials were not changed for several years.

3.8 Ink-jet printing with water-based ink

We studied a modification method of polymeric films (PP, PE, PET, PC, etc.) suitable for usual ink-jet printing with water-based ink.

Fig.12 Time-change in water-based paint coating on silicone rubbers; upper two lines: corona-discharged ones, and lower one: modified ones by the present method, the numbers give the time after the treatment.

It needed to change some treatment conditions. Examined polymeric films or sheets could be printed by usual ink-jet printers. Although untreated PET, PP, PE, PC films were not printed at all, modified films were printed clearly by ink-jet printers with water-based ink. Figure 13 gives an example of untreated PET sheet printed by an ink-jet printer.

Fig.13 Untreated PET film printed by an ink-jet printer.

Figure 14 gives a modified PET film printed by the ink-jet printer. Although the untreated PET sheet was not printed at all, the modified one gave a good printing with water-based ink.

Fig.14 Modified PET sheet printed by an ink-jet printer.

Figure 15 gives a modified PP film printed by the ink-jet printer with water-based ink. The modified PP film was printed well but untreated PP ones were

Figure 16 gives modified PC sheets were also printed clearly by the ink-jet printer with water-based ink. The PC film was printed very clearly.

Fig.15 Modified PP sheet printed by an ink-jet printer.

Fig.16 Modified PC sheet printed by an ink-jet printer.

4. Conclusion

The present process gave durable modified properties as compared with usual corona or plasma discharge treatments and other methods. Especially, modified materials can be adhered to each other or to other materials using any adhesives, even after they are laid for several months. Modified fibers were useful for preparing composite materials (FRP). The modified polymeric materials are useful in many fields.

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